

ART3MIS: RAY-BASED TEXTUAL ANNOTATION ON 3D CULTURAL OBJECTS

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Abstract

Beyond the simplistic three-dimensional (3D) visualisation, archaeologists, as well as cultural heritage experts and practitioners, need applications with advanced functionalities, such as the annotation and the attachment of metadata on particular regions of the 3D digital objects. Various approaches have been presented to tackle this challenge, most of them achieving excellent results in the domain of their application, confined, though, in that specific domain and particular problem. In this paper, we present ART3mis, a general-purpose, user-friendly, interactive textual annotation tool for 3D objects, which is primarily attuned to aid cultural heritage conservators, restorers, and curators with no technical skills in 3D imaging and graphics, in easily handling, segmenting, and annotating 3D digital replicas of artefacts. ART3mis applies a user-driven, direct-on-surface approach and is able to handle detailed 3D cultural objects in real-time and store textual annotations for multiple complex regions in JSON data format.

Keywords: 3D object annotation, user-driven characterization, cultural heritage application

Introduction

As 3D objects are progressively becoming pervasive in archaeology and cultural heritage applications, enhanced functionalities surpassing the simplistic 3D visualisation are required all the more. Among the first and most fundamental such requirements is the attachment of metadata on top of the 3D replica of a cultural object and the capability of a multi-layered representation. To be able to provide such rich environments for visualisation and

study, those systems need to be complemented or coupled with what is called annotation functionalities.

3D object annotation is the process of selecting a region over a 3D surface and linking that region to a high-level representation either in structured or in free form. Annotation on 3D objects is typically considered in two forms, (a) as an automated feature or semantics-based region segmentation (Nousias et al. 2020), (b) as a manually, or, in some cases, computer-assisted, selected region characterisation (Arnaoutoglou et al. 2003).

While the former relates to automated semantics extraction for various computer vision and graphics applications, the latter is most suited to cultural heritage applications, like conservation. In this scenario, 3D objects are presented to experts, which are called to annotate either the various degradation effects on a reconstructed object's surface (humidity damage, surface cracks and fissures), or any restoration processes that took place (preservation information, mended areas, cleaning process) (Ponchio et al. 2020; Soler et al. 2013). Additionally, materials and information concerning decoration can also be annotated.

Since there has been no standardisation in this field, each project and research team typically come up with a new idea, method, and approach to implement an annotation tool that is usually domain- or, even, problem-specific. There is also no standardisation on how the annotations are stored, that is, how the metadata are recorded, thus having today a diverse set of approaches and solutions. Among the most challenging issues in implementing a 3D annotation system are (a) the user interaction design, (b) the input conversion and association, (c) the management of high-resolution 3D data, (d) the representation schemes, (e) the annotation format and data handling, and (f) the annotation as a Web application (Ponchio et al. 2020).

ART3mis was originally developed to tackle those challenges, and to provide a user-friendly, interactive, textual annotation tool for 3D cultural objects for heritage conservators. The idea originated in the EU project WARMEST1, where an annotation

tool was needed for the annotation of the various degradations on the 3D models of the columns in the Patio de los Leones, in the UNESCO World Heritage Site of Alhambra, Granada, Spain. As the tool was required for scientific use by experts with no technical skills in 3D imaging and graphics, ART3mis had to follow the intuitive What You See Is What You Get (WYSIWYG) design and be able to handle easily, intuitively and in real-time the various 3D models created by the 3D digitisation of the monument. Image-based digitisation was employed, and highly detailed 3D replicas had been created (Pavlidis et al. 2007), thus models of high polygon counts needed to be handled in real-time. Although ART3mis was primarily tested with the WARMEST 3D models, it was also tested with other 3D models with geometry in the range of 20 million polygons.

The structure of this paper is as follows: Section 2 is a brief description of the background and the related work regarding 3D object annotation over its surface. Section 3 presents ART3mis, the features and the annotating approach. Finally, Section 4 summarises the work and discusses future perspectives.

1. Background and related work

Methodologically, annotations can be attached either to single points, lines, voxels, or regions on a 3D object's surface. In other words, based on the data types, the following types of annotations are defined: (a) on the surface of the objects (3D mesh), as collections of polygons or points, (b) on

the texture of the objects, in UV-space, apparently leading to a 2D annotation approach, (c) on a hybrid space, fusing annotation on 2D images with reprojection techniques to transfer the annotations in 3D space, and (d) on the voxel space, as collections of voxels. For a detailed presentation of the various approaches, the interested reader may refer to (Ponchio et al. 2020).

Focusing entirely on the annotation on the surface of the objects (case a, above), the process consists of collecting the user-defined regions of interest (ROIs) and defining those regions as 3D mesh subsets. This can either be based on *segmentation* or *trimming* of the 3D model. Segmentation is the selection of a set of polygons on the original 3D model, whereas trimming requires the modification of the polygons in order to fit the user-selected region. The trimmed region is always a subset of the corresponding segmented region. Apparently, trimming may support a more accurate region selection but requires a much more complex process. In addition, the process changes the 3D mesh in order to fit the selected region, thus it is an interventional method.

ShapeAnnotator2 (Attene et al. 2009) is a tool that matches a 3D object with instances of ontology classes, utilising multiple automatic segmentation algorithms and providing an ontology browser. The user is provided the means to edit the ROIs and the results are saved in an OWL file.

3D-COFORM (Serna et al. 2012) is the first interactive semantic enrichment tool based on the CIDOC-CRM ontology. The region selection is performed by using 3D

primitives, such as spheres or cylinders, as well as by outlining contours on the surface of the 3D model. Furthermore, 3D-COFORM has been designed in a way that, with the usage of a shared repository multiple users can work on the same 3D model.

The *3D Semantic Association (3DSA)* (Yu and Hunter 2013) is a Web system, which enables the analysis of 3D cultural objects based on specific ontologies, supporting annotation which may also be semantically assisted. The selection of ROIs is based on user-defined polygonal shapes or 3D volumetric segments overlaid on the rendered model. The underlying ontology in the system provides the potential to support high level semantics and inferences.

POTREE3 (Schütz 2015) is a Web viewer for 3D point clouds that is equipped with a number of measurement tools for large point clouds. POTREE seems to support only point-based annotation, with descriptions that can be edited in an HTML file. POTREE has the potential to be used as the base engine for the development of more focused Web-based annotation application.

CHER-Ob (Shi et al. 2016) is a heritage object analysis tool that also supports 3D mesh annotations. Annotations are based on rectangular region selections and can either correspond to surface patches or parts of the 3D model. It should be noted that *CHER-Ob* is a complete content management system with additional analysis tools for artefacts.

ClippingVolumes (Ponchio et al. 2020) is an advanced annotation approach, supporting arbitrary shaped user-defined region selections. The innovation in this method, is in the de-termination of the correct surface

to be selected. As known, when selecting 3D surfaces on a 2D screen the distance of the selected region from the viewer (depth) is unknown. Usually, the desired surface is the one currently rendered, thus there has to be a mechanism to define the depth based on the rendered surfaces. In this method, this problem is addressed by defining an arbitrary bounding polyhedron, which is minimised in an iterative manner. The storage of the annotations is supported by a content management system.

Main challenge in developing a 3D mesh-based annotation tool is in providing the capability of selecting arbitrarily shaped ROIs using friendly interaction methods, while relying on interoperability standards of the stored data. The lack of an easy-to-use complex region annotation tool has led to the development of ART3mis.

2. ART3mis

ART3mis is using the direct-on-surface annotation approach, by providing various ways of selecting a ROI on an object's 3D model surface. It should be noted that ART3mis works on the textured 3D model, which is a method that has been largely discussed in the relevant literature as the most appropriate, as in many cases the texture assists in more accurate identification of defects or degradations on materials for conservation applications. In addition, it supports not only the one-time annotation but also the processing of previous annotations, consisting of a complete annotation management tool. The annotation storage strategy selected in this

case was that of a JSON4 structured text file, which is a technique that becomes pervasive in today's Web-connected systems.

Due to the target group of heritage conservators with no technical skills in 3D imaging and graphics, we followed the WYSIWYG philosophy and the 10 heuristic principles that describe a user-friendly interface (Nielsen and Molich 1990):

1. Visibility of system status
2. Match the system and the real world
3. User control freedom
4. Consistency and standards
5. Error prevention
6. Recognition rather than recall
7. Flexibility and efficiency of use
8. Aesthetic and minimalist design
9. Help users recognize, diagnose, and recover from error
10. Help and documentation

ART3mis supports two modes of ROI selection: (a) brush or painting selection and (b) polyline or lasso selection. A graphical representation of the basic process of mesh selection is shown in Figure 1. It is emphasised that in either of the two modes of operation, selection of ROIs in ART3mis is based on a two-step process, including (a) the sketching of the region on the screen and (b) the selection of 3D polygons that correspond to the parts of the 3D mesh bound or defined by the sketched region using ray-polygon intersection. In the field of computer graphics, ray-polygon intersection is the act of finding any or all points that simultaneously lie on a particular ray and a

particular polygon (Glassner 1989), thus it represents a mature and successful approach in selecting parts of a 3D mesh that are currently visible.

In addition, Figure 2 shows the JSON file structure that stores the ART3mis

annotations. As shown, each ROI is described with a group of three fields: the colour (the preselected representation colour), the text (the main annotation text), and the polygons’ indices (the ROI on the 3D mesh).

Figure 1: Ray-polygon intersection–based ROI selection approach in ART3mis.

Figure 2: The JSON file structure in ART3mis.

In brush selection, a brush tool is used to paint on the screen. The width of the brush is user-defined. As soon as the user stops painting with the brush, ART3mis applies

ray-polygon intersection with a pre-defined or adaptive resolution, initially set to 1 ray per screen pixel. This is applies only to the visible surfaces. As ray-polygon intersection is a complex and resource consuming method, chances are that polygons might be missed in the path of the tracing, resulting in a selection region with “holes” (missed polygons). Thus, after ray-polygon intersection, a selection volume is defined by the minimum and maximum coordinates of the identified polygons and the polygon se-lection is further refined in order to address the issue of missing polygons as shown in Figure 1.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3: Annotating: (a) cracks with the brush selection, and (b) overlapping regions with the lasso selection.

In lasso selection, the user may draw a freeform shape bounding the ROI on the visible 3D mesh. Lasso selection is in essence a multiple application of brush selections. Every selected region is decomposed into elementary horizontal regions, in which ray-polygon intersection is applied, one after the other, until all the region has been scanned. Currently, the lasso selection is limited to defining convex regions, thus complex concave shapes are supported by using the brush selection method.

Figure 3 shows examples of the two types of annotation supported by ART3mis, in which models from the SHREC 2021 dataset (Sipiran et al. 2021) were used. The brush selection on a 3D model with cracks is shown

in Figure 3-(a), whereas the lasso selection of overlapping ROIs is shown in Figure 3-(b).

2.a ART3mis implementation specifics

ART3mis utilises a geometry processing library called libigl 5 . Specifically, the selection of a ROI is based on the Embree6 ray casting algorithm. Moreover, Dear ImGui7 is responsible for the intuitive GUI design. Currently, ART3mis supports OBJ files for textured 3D models and saves the annotations in JSON format. It currently runs on Microsoft Windows. Unlike relevant software, the ART3mis development approach focused on keeping the balance between a user-friendly design and a fully featured annotation application. To this end, the application presents 4 main information frames, as described below and shown in Figure 4:

- **Main toolbar:** The typical toolbar for the file loading/saving, the user’s preferences, and the user documentation help.
- **Tools frame:** The list of options for the annotation tools and their settings.
- **Properties frame:** The list of all current 3D model annotations.
- **Corner frame:** The system information frame, including the rendering frames per second, the 3D model information (number of vertices and polygons), the number of selected polygons, the name of the selected saved region and the mouse position.

Compared with similar annotation systems, in which the users select a rectangular region or a volume of a 3D model (Shi et al.

2016), ART3mis provides more flexible user-friendly and intuitive tools, which also support fast and accurate annotation.

2.b ART3mis workflow

The annotation process in ART3mis begins with the loading of a 3D model and of any information associated with it, such as texture or saved annotations. Manipulation of the loaded 3D model is done in a typical manner adopted in most 3D viewing or modelling applications with mouse-keyboard interactions, supporting rotation, pan and zoom. Mouse interactions are also used for the selection of the ROIs on which to apply the annotations, using the two selection modes defined in previous sections (brush and lasso). After selection of a ROI, the user inputs the associated annotation and saves the result. Repeating and saving updates the annotation file and the presented list of annotations in the properties' information frame. Editing of previous annotations is as easy as selecting the annotation from the list and editing the associated text.

Figure 5 shows an example of selecting a new ROI for annotation using the lasso tool. Step-by-step, the region is defined, the polygons selected, and the textual annotation attached.

3. Conclusions and future work

ART3mis is a new 3D model annotation tool that is currently in a Windows portable implementation and supports user-friendly, real-time, multiple JSON-encoded simple text annotations on high-resolution 3D models. It follows the WYSIWYG philosophy and the 10 heuristic principles that describe a user-friendly environment. The ART3mis region selection engine is based on a novel ray-polygon intersection and selection volume approach that ensures accurate real-time 3D mesh selection. ART3mis can be further improved by supporting rich text annotations, more 3D file formats, more diverse selection tools, trimming operations, and platform independence, especially towards a cross-platform Web-based deployment.

Figure 4: The main information frames of ART3mis.

Figure 5: New region annotation workflow in ART3mis: (a) lasso-based selection, (b) definition of the ROI as a mesh sub-set, and (c) the textual annotation and its settings.

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1 Project WARMEST website @ <https://warmestproject.eu/>.

2 ShapeAnnotator webpage @ <http://shapeannotator.sourceforge.net>.

3 POTREE webpage @ <https://potree.github.io>.

4 C++ Library JSON website @ <https://github.com/nlohmann/json>.

5 C++ Library libigl website @ <https://libigl.github.io/>.

6 Ray tracing embree website @ <https://www.embree.org/>.

7 Graphical User Interface Dear ImGui website @ <https://github.com/ocornut/imgui>.